

Halogenation. Part IX. Bromination of Pseudocumene.

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By the action of bromine on pseudocumene in the cold nuclear substituted bromo derivatives and in sunlight in the cold a light oil and on heating to 160° pseudocumene dibromide and pseudocumene tribromide have been obtained (Beilstein, *Annalen*, 1866, 137, 323; Fittig, *Annalen*, 1869, 151, 267; Schram, *Ber.*, 1886, 9, 217; Jacobsen, *Ber.*, 1888, 21, 2822; Hjelt and Gadd, *Ber.*, 1886, 19, 868).

We have obtained in sunlight either pseudocumene monobromide alone or a mixture of monobromide, dibromide and tribromide of pseudocumene depending on the conditions of the experiment. By brominating 5-bromopseudocumene in sunlight, only nuclear substituted derivatives of pseudocumene have been obtained. At the boiling temperature of pseudocumene in the diffused day light, only monobromide is obtained even when there is a considerable excess of bromine present. Comparatively good yields of the nuclear substituted bromo derivatives of pseudocumene are obtained, if bromination is carried on in presence of strong or fuming sulphuric acid or strong or fuming nitric acid or a mixture of nitro-sulphonic and fuming nitric acids.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A mixture of pseudocumene (10 c.c.) and bromine (4.5 c.c.) was exposed to sunlight for about 3 hours. The reaction product was then heated further for 2 hours on a water-bath under reflux. The product was first washed thrice with 1% solution of sodium carbonate, then with water, dried over anhydrous calcium chloride and distilled at 152-56°/30 mm, yield 5.1 g. It is an oily lachrymatory substance. It darkens in colour on standing and becomes almost black after a few days. It decomposes on boiling at the ordinary pressure. (Found: Br, 41.2. C_6H_3 (Me_2CH_2Br requires Br, 40.2 per cent).

If exposure to sunlight was followed by heating on a water-bath, only monobromide was obtained whereas if it was followed by heating on a paraffin-bath to about the boiling point of pseudocumene, a mixture of mono-, di-, and tribromide was obtained, their relative proportions increasing by using bromine (3 to 6 c.c.).

Working in the same way with 5-bromopseudocumene in sunlight, followed by heating for about 3 hours on a water or a paraffin-bath only di- and trinuclear substituted bromo derivatives in fairly good yields were obtained.

If strong or fuming sulphuric acid or strong or fuming nitric acid or a mixture of nitrosulphonic and fuming nitric acid was added little at a time to a mixture of pseudocumene and bromine and the products formed examined after 3-4 hours, much better yield of the nuclear substituted bromo derivatives was obtained. The best yield (3-bromopseudocumene, 4.3 g ; 5-bromopseudocumene, 2.8 g. ; 5:6-dibromopseudocumene, 1.2 g; and 3:5:6-tribromopseudocumene 2.2 g., from 10 c.c. of pseudocumene) was, however, obtained when bromination was carried on in presence of a mixture of nitrosulphonic and fuming nitric acids (10 c.c.)